

THE CULTURAL DIMENSION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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ABSTRACT

This article presents research conducted in the field of phraseology its relation to culture. The article specifically focuses on cultural specific meaning of phraseological units and presents different idioms and their meanings. The article also analyzes their origins and reasons.

Introduction

Language is not only a means of communication but also a mirror of the culture and values of the community that uses it. One linguistic phenomenon that demonstrates the close relationship between language and culture is the use of phraseological units. These fixed expressions often convey meanings that cannot be understood solely from the meanings of their individual components. Many phraseological units contain culturally specific elements, reflecting a nation's traditions, historical experiences, beliefs, and geographical environment. As a result, they serve as important carriers of cultural knowledge and identity.

Analysis and results

According to v.a.maslova a close relationship phraseological units with background knowledge of native speakers, with cultural - historical traditions of the people speaking this language. Phraseological combinations related subjects attributed symptoms that are associated with a certain view of the world, express their attitude to them and give them a rating [3]. She asserts that phraseological units reflect national and cultural values; regarded as the soul of each national language; they express the spirit of the language and the uniqueness of the people. [1]. The following idioms are analyzed as examples:

-pandora's box- something that creates a lot of new problems that you did not expect [11]

The origin of idiom related to greek mythology the god prometheus stole fire from heaven to give to the human race, which originally consisted only of men. To punish humanity, the other gods created the first woman, the beautiful pandora. As a gift, zeus gave her a box, which she was told never to open. However, as soon as he was out of sight she took off the lid, and out swarmed all the troubles of the world, never to be recaptured. Only hope was left in the box, stuck under the lid. Anything that looks

ordinary but may produce unpredictable harmful results can thus be called a pandora's box. [13]

-to carry coals to newcastle- to supply something to a place or person that already has a lot of that particular thing. [12]

It refers to the fact that, historically, the economy of newcastle upon tyne in north-eastern england was a great center of coal shipments from nearby mines, and therefore any attempt to sell coal to newcastle would be foolhardy as supply would be greater there than anywhere else in britain. Similarly, newcastle, new south wales (named after the northeastern city) has one of the largest coal ports in the world, and hence it would also be meaningless to ship coals there. [14]

Conclusion

In conclusion, the analysis of phraseological units demonstrates that they originate from various historical, cultural, religious, and social sources. As the examples discussed in this study illustrate, phraseological units are closely connected with culture-specific meanings and reflect the values, beliefs, traditions, and worldview of a particular linguistic community.

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